

LONELY-EU Policy Brief Series
Policy Update

LONELY-EU

**Guidelines for formulating
evidence-based policy
recommendations on
Social Isolation and Loneliness**

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Executive Summary

Evidence-based policy recommendations on social isolation and loneliness

Effective policy on social isolation and loneliness depends on how research evidence is translated into action. This policy brief provides practical guidelines for formulating evidence-based policy recommendations within the LONELY-EU project.

The guidelines are designed to help policymakers and policy advisors work with research evidence in a transparent, realistic, and usable way. They do not prescribe policymakers specific interventions. Instead, they clarify how evidence can inform policy choices, while acknowledging uncertainty, context, and implementation constraints.

Key principles include:

- being explicit about the evidence base and its limits,
- communicating uncertainty rather than masking it,
- matching recommendations to policy scope and capacity,
- clearly specifying target groups and contexts.

To support consistency and clarity, the guidelines propose a step-by-step approach from evidence to recommendation. This approach ensures that policy recommendations are grounded in research findings, explicit about trade-offs, and transparent how certain policymakers can be about the evidence.

The Evidence-to-Action (E2A) Board plays a central role in this process by providing structured feedback on draft recommendations and helping align research outputs with policy needs at EU, national, and local levels.

By applying these guidelines, LONELY-EU aims to strengthen the dialogue between research, policy, and practice, and to support policymakers in making informed decisions on social isolation and loneliness.

Purpose of this policy brief

This policy brief sets out practical guidelines for translating research evidence on social isolation and loneliness into policy recommendations that are credible, transparent, and usable.

The guidelines are developed within the LONELY-EU project together with the Evidence-to-Action (E2A) Board and other policy stakeholders. They are designed to support policymakers at EU, national, and local level in working with research evidence in a structured and realistic way.

The focus is not on producing “one-size-fits-all” solutions, but on improving how evidence is interpreted, communicated, and applied in different policy contexts.

How to use these guidelines

These guidelines are intended to be used:

- when formulating policy recommendations based on LONELY-EU research outputs,
- when reviewing draft recommendations for clarity and policy relevance,
- when discussing evidence with policymakers and practitioners.

They can be applied to policy briefs, background notes, presentations, and consultations.

They do not replace political decision-making, but aim to improve the quality and transparency of the evidence that informs it.

Core principles

Be explicit about the evidence base

Policy recommendations should clearly state:

- which data sources are used,
- whether findings are based on single studies, multiple studies, or systematic reviews,
- whether evidence is observational, experimental, or model-based.

This helps policymakers understand what kind of confidence is warranted and avoids overstating what the evidence can support.

Communicate uncertainty and limitations

Uncertainty is inherent in research on social isolation and loneliness.

Policy recommendations should therefore:

- indicate the strength of the evidence,
- clarify remaining uncertainties,
- avoid presenting estimates or projections as precise predictions.

Being explicit about uncertainty strengthens, rather than weakens, the credibility of recommendations.

Match recommendations to policy scope and capacity

Recommendations should be proportionate to:

- the level of government addressed (EU, national, local),
- existing policy competences,
- available implementation capacity.

Where evidence suggests promising interventions that exceed current capacities, this should be stated explicitly rather than implied.

Specify the target population and context

Policy recommendations should clearly indicate:

- which population groups are addressed,
- which contexts are assumed (e.g. labour market, education, health, urban or rural settings),
- whether findings are expected to generalise across countries or are context-specific.

This avoids misapplication of evidence to settings for which it was not intended.

From evidence to recommendation: a step-by-step approach

To support consistency across LONELY-EU outputs, policy recommendations should follow a common logic:

Summarise the relevant evidence

- Briefly describe the key findings and their empirical basis.

Interpret implications for policy

- Explain what the findings suggest for policy goals or priorities, without prescribing specific actions too early.

Identify trade-offs and constraints

- Highlight potential costs, unintended effects, or implementation challenges.

Formulate the recommendation

- Present the recommendation in clear, non-technical language.

Clarify confidence and scope

- Indicate how robust the recommendation is and under which conditions it is expected to hold.

This structure supports transparency and makes recommendations easier to assess and compare.

Role of the Evidence-to-Action (E2A) Board

The E2A Board plays a central role in applying these guidelines by:

- reviewing draft recommendations for clarity and policy relevance,
- providing feedback on whether interpretations are justified by the evidence,
- identifying mismatches between research timelines and policy needs.

The Board does not validate political choices, but helps ensure that recommendations are evidence-informed and clearly framed.

Transparency and limits

Evidence-based policy recommendations are not neutral or final answers.

They reflect:

- available data at a given point in time,
- methodological choices,
- normative assumptions about policy goals.

For this reason, LONELY-EU recommendations should always make explicit:

- what the evidence can support,
- what remains uncertain,
- where political judgment is required.

Concluding note

By following these guidelines, LONELY-EU aims to improve the dialogue between research, policy, and practice.

Clearer recommendations, explicit assumptions, and transparent communication of uncertainty are essential for effective policymaking on social isolation and loneliness.

GLOSSARY

Loneliness

A subjective experience of lacking desired social connection, regardless of the number of social contacts.

Social isolation

An objective condition characterised by limited social contacts or interactions.

Evidence (in this brief)

Empirical findings from research, data analyses, evaluations or monitoring systems that are sufficiently robust to inform policy decisions.

Monitoring framework

A structured system for regularly tracking levels, patterns and risk factors of loneliness and social isolation across populations and over time.

Policy recommendation

Actionable guidance for policymakers that is based on evidence, adapted to context, and proportionate to the strength of the available data.

Evidence-to-Action (E2A) Board

A multi-stakeholder advisory body within LONELY-EU that connects research, policy and practice through structured feedback and dialogue.

Uncertainty

The degree to which evidence is incomplete, variable or context-dependent, and therefore requires cautious interpretation in policymaking.

About LONELY-EU

LONELY-EU is a Horizon Europe project that aims to improve understanding, monitoring and policymaking on social isolation and loneliness across Europe. The project combines research, policy development and networking to support evidence-based action at all governance levels.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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